

GENERAL ISSUES OF DEVELOPMENT OF LINGUISTIC COMPETENCE OF PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS THROUGH ADJECTIVE WORD GROUPS

¹Jalilova Dilshoda Ural kizi, ²Sa'dullayeva Sevinch, ³Risqulova Maftuna, ⁴Ravshanova
Diyora

¹TSPU named after Nizami, teacher of the department of mother tongue and its teaching
methodology in primary education

²TSPU named after Nizami, Faculty of Elementary Education students

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11094056>

Abstract. *This article focuses on the general issues of developing the linguistic competence of elementary school students regarding adjective vocabulary in elementary school mother tongue classes. In particular, the methods and tools used for the formation of linguistic competence in terms of adjective vocabulary in elementary school students are also discussed.*

Keywords: *competence, language competence, linguistic analysis, phonetics, quality, grammatical analysis, linguistics.*

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev: "Since the first years of independence, special attention has been paid to the fundamental reform of the education system in our country, to ensure that our children acquire modern knowledge and skills at the level of world standards, and become physically and mentally mature people. "Great work is being done to raise the population, to reveal their abilities and talents, intellectual potential, to raise the feelings of loyalty and devotion to the Motherland in the hearts of the young generation,"[1] he said. at the meeting dedicated to the issues of further development and improvement of tests for admission to the bachelor's course of higher education. Based on the words of the head of state, it can be said that the changes and reforms implemented throughout the country naturally increase the demand for the formation of types of competence in students during the education process. In today's educational processes, in order for students to become mature in all aspects, it is necessary to conduct a deep research in this regard and take practical actions in accordance with the results of the research. In particular, in order to improve students' knowledge of vocabulary in primary education and to form linguistic competences in terms of quality vocabulary, first of all, it is permissible to look at the history of its methodological development.

In this process, first of all, the role of native language classes in the formation of young representatives of the younger generation, the ability to fluently express meaningful and beautiful thoughts without grammatical and stylistic errors, and another important aspect - the ability to write correctly without spelling errors, is extremely important. it must be admitted. Meaningful and correct organization of mother tongue lessons in primary education, teachers' skillful emphasis on linguistic analysis in these lessons, in order to develop students' skills in the listed tasks, the importance of being able to give is high. That is why linguistic analysis is given a place in the primary mother tongue program of mother tongue classes organized in today's school system.

Currently, the existing education system in the republic is trying to move from the traditional knowledge-based education model to the competence-based model. One of the main reasons for this is the methodical manual created for science teachers in the "Mother Tongue"

textbooks of elementary grades or the concept or some direction related to the issues of forming linguistic analysis skills in students or teaching linguistic analysis in the complexes. not given. But if you study the research of scientists who have conducted research in the Russian education system, you can see that it is paid attention to in some sense. For example, Professor E. A. Bystrov says, "At the national school, attention should be paid to the approach based on competence to the approach based on knowledge»[2]. According to the scientist, all this will lead to a change in the educational paradigm. These students are mainly known for having the ability to apply the acquired knowledge in various life situations.

One of the important tasks facing today's modern school is the huge task of educating a literate person who knows the state language at a high level. It is in primary education that the foundation of literacy is laid. Because during this period, intensive training is conducted on all types of speech activities (writing, reading, speaking and listening). According to M.V. Dubova, "primary education should perceive and implement new ideas of the competence-based approach earlier and more actively than other levels of education»[3].

Methodists, psychologists, teachers and linguists say that they have studied the implementation of the competency-based approach in the educational system and its various aspects in their various researches. In particular, in the works of A.G. Asmolov, L.B. Antipina, G.M. Bogomazov, A.A. Verbitsky, D.S. Ermakov, E.V. Kon'kov, I.A. Zimnyaya, E.V. Golubskaya, G.A. Orlova, N.M. Shansky, one can see views and opinions about the essence of the competency-based approach.

The formation of linguistic competences is also considered important in the teaching of the mother tongue in the public education system. N.M. Shansky supports the competent use of language tools in accordance with literary standards. N.M. Shansky tries to formulate ideas about how language works, what it is and how it changes.

It is very important to know the theory in the field of language in the formation of linguistic competences in terms of quality vocabulary in elementary school students. A pedagogue who knows the semantic, morphological, syntactic categories that represent an interacting and organized system related to different levels of the language will have no problems teaching students the correct use of language units and the rules of their connection.

Linguistic competence is the result of students' understanding of speech experience, which, in turn, includes knowledge of the basics of the science of the native language, and it is not unreasonable to include the acquisition of a set of linguistic concepts. It also involves learning the elements of the history of science about the native language, its famous representatives, and information about the place of the language in the life of the society. Constant interest, respect and love for this subject are formed through mother tongue lessons.

In primary education, it is necessary to organize the process of formation of linguistic competences in terms of adjective vocabulary in the mother tongue classes, taking into account the competence-based approach, and it is also necessary to remember that the acquisition of language knowledge by primary school students is a - contains an integral system, not in the form of separate parts. It is necessary to form a scientific understanding of the levels of the language system (phonetic, lexical, morphological, syntactic), its internal relations, and the features of its application in the primary education itself. It is important to thoroughly study a new language unit, its function in the language system, and its use in a communicative situation.

It is necessary to take into account the fact that the quality is one of the means of linguistic expressiveness in describing the surrounding reality, and it is distinguished by the richness of grammatical forms in the formation of linguistic competences in terms of adjectives in elementary school students. It is impossible to imagine any sentence without the words in this part of the speech. The use of adjectives can cause difficulties for younger students. This is due to the large semantic potential of some units, students' inability to prioritize short forms of adjectives and forms of comparative degrees.

There are aspects that should be given importance in the formation of linguistic competence in elementary school students, and for this reason, the formation of linguistic competence in young students is appropriate if it is carried out in the following directions:

- strengthening and expanding knowledge about qualities;
- to develop practical skills of analyzing an adjective noun as a part of a sentence;
- development of the skills of using adjectives in speech, taking into account the normative aspect.

In addition to the above, it will be useful to refer to various methods and methods of a problem-creative and research nature in the course of elementary school mother tongue lessons. In this case, targeted and systematic use is appropriate. The acquisition of linguistic information about the name of the quality is effectively carried out taking into account the functional and communicative direction when working with the text.

In conclusion, it can be said that the mentioned methods of working with the text create an opportunity to organize complex work to strengthen the learned material about quality as a part of speech, to develop the ability to use adjectives without violating lexical compatibility in speech. This, in turn, helps to effectively form linguistic competence. In addition, studying the works of scientists who have conducted research on competence will also help in creating a set of effective methods for forming linguistic competence in elementary school students and using it effectively.

REFERENCES

1. Almatov T. Yadgorov Q, Pochchayeva G. "O'zbek tili o'qitish metodikasi" metodik qo'llanma. Jizzax 2016 y.
2. «Ta'lim sohasini isloh qilish, kasb-hunar ta'limi tizimini yanada rivojlantirish va oliy ta'limning bakalavr yo'nalishiga qabul bo'yicha test sinovlarini takomillashtirish masalalari». Yig'ilish. 9-oktyabr, 2017-y.
3. U.Tursunov, B.O'rinboyev "O'zbek adabiy tili tarixi", Toshkent. "O'qituvchi". 2012.
4. Быстрова Е.А. Цели обучения русскому языку, или какую компетенцию мы формируем на уроках// Обучение русскому языку в школе учеб. Пособие для студентов педагогических вузов Е.А.Быстрова, С.И.Лылова, В.И.Капинос, — М. Дрофа, 2004. - С. 20-39.
5. Дубова М.В. Дидактические принципы компетентностно ориентированного обучения в начальном общем образовании // Начальное образование. — 2012. — №1. - С. 50-51.